

BENDING AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIORS OF CNF/PPy CONDUCTIVE SINGLE-LAYER COMPOSITE SENSORS

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1 Introduction

Conductive polymers attract researchers with their good electromechanical performances. They are suitable to be used as smart materials for actuators and sensors. The volume change (i.e., strain) in CPs is caused by doping and dedoping of counter ions during a redox reaction [1]. Some researchers focused on the reinforcement of CP with metal fibers of carbon fibers. CNFs have a high stiffness and strength, good thermal and electrical conductivities were reported recently [2], what make it possible to be used as a reinforce fiber. CNF/PPy film has been fabricated in a physical method by Kim and Zhang [3]; however the flexibility was not good. Wang et al. [4] and Sabsiena et al. [5] fabricated monolithic polyaniline actuators with a long lifetime (>3000 cycles). Han and Shi [6] developed a single-layer PPy film which can operate a bending actuation and investigated its behaviors. Toi and Jung used an ionic transportation equation to analysis the motion of ions in order to investigate the actuation of a polypyrrole-based actuator [7]. Most of CP bending actuators consists of bi- or tri-layers. The bending actuation usually caused by the actuation difference between different layers.

In this study, single-layer PPy film and CNF/PPy composite films were fabricated by the electrochemical polymerization process, and then their electrical conductivities and bending deformations were measured. The CNF/PPy composite film was especially developed for the first time in this study. We demonstrated convincingly that a single-layer CNF/PPy composite film can be bent without bi- or tri-layers structure, which makes this finding be differentiated from other previous works. Electrical conductivity was measured by the four-probe method. Mechanical properties are obtained by a UTM (Instron Universal Testing Machine 3343). In order to investigate the

electrochemical behaviors of PPy and CNF/PPy composite films, an equation about the electrochemical behavior was developed. In this paper, the equation is based on the size of a single ion. Although there are some research articles on the derivation of equations about the electrochemical behaviors, none of them focus on the volume of a single ion. The results found in this research show that PPy and CNF/PPy film can be used as smart materials for actuators or sensors.

During actuation, the sample films were soaked in a LiTFSI (Bis(trifluoromethane)-sulfonimide lithium salt)/ Propylene carbonate solution, and the TFSI ions transport in the solution freely. When the electrical potential is given, ions move to doping or dedoping the film following the electrical force. In fact, there is a redox reaction taken place on the film, but not a simple movement of ions. The ions dope into the polymer during the oxidation process. The bending actuation is imperfect. The reason of this phenomenon is because of the oxidation reaction and reduction reactions are not in balance.

2 Fabrications of PPy and CNF/PPy Films

2.1 PPy Film

Details for fabrication of single layer PPy films are introduced in this section. To fabricate a PPy film, pyrrole, propylene carbonate and LiTFSI are needed. Pyrrole is the main raw material, it will form the polypyrrole, LiTFSI will be used as counter ions to keep the balance of charging. Propylene carbonate is used as solvent in which ions can move freely. 10ml liquid pyrrole monomer (measured by burette) was added to a propylene carbonate (50ml) solution of LiTFSI (4g) the solution is storage in a little beaker. The 3cm x 4cm nickel (Ni) sheets were prepared for

working and counter electrodes. The distance between two electrodes is fixed to be 3mm. After prepare the solution, the fixed electrode will immerse in the solution. A DC power supply ADPS-503D was used to supply a constant current. Anode was connected to the working electrode and cathode was connected to the counter electrode. Polymerization took place under 0°C. During polymerization, the color of solution changed from colorless to light brown for a while, and turned to dark black finally. The change of color denote the oxidation process, before oxidation, the solution is colorless, then, it change to light brown after partly oxidation, when the color change to dark black, it means the pyrrole is oxidized completely.

PPy can be deposited on both sides of the working electrode; however, polymerization on the side facing the counter electrode is more likely to proceed than the other side. The reason of this phenomenon is the current density in this side is higher than the other side. Therefore, PPy films on that side were used for various sample tests. Fig. 1 shows a schematic drawing for polymerization and electrophoretic deposition processes. In this figure the electrode is noted by two faced Ni sheet, one is working electrode (connect with anode) and the other is counter electrode (connect with cathode). The distance between working electrode and counter electrode is 2mm and be fixed with wood blocks and tape. Fig. 2 shows the pictures of the experiment setup.

Fig. 1 The schematic drawing of an electrophoretic deposition process

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 Pictures for the fabrication process

2.2 CNF/PPy Film

To fabricate the CNF/PPy films, the working electrode was pretreated with CNF dispersion in advance. The Ni electrode (3cm x 4cm) was soaked in a CNF/water solution in order to paste CNF to one surface of the electrode. CNF dispersion will sHeating the electrode on a hotplate to make water evaporated, only CNF was left on the Ni electrode. The CNF coating was then removed on the back surface of the working electrode and only CNF on the front side facing a counter electrode was left for following polymerization.

Weights of electrodes with and without CNF coatings were measured to get the net weight of CNF deposited on an electrode. The fabrication process is based on the oxidation of pyrrole monomers in the mixed solution of propylene carbonate (PC) and LiTFSI under a given voltage. The CNF weight ratio can be controlled by polymerization time. The polypyrrole will polymerize more and more by time. The electrode coated with CNF was used as a working electrode. The weight difference between electrode coated with

CNF and naked electrode is measured by an electrical balance, which is the exact weight of CNF. Polymerization rate is measured through several times of electrochemical processing. The surface with CNF faced the counter electrode and a CNF/PPy film was obtained on this side. CNF/PPy films with the CNF weight ratios of 3%, 5%, 7% and 10% were fabricated. All film samples were peeled off from the working electrode after polymerization and immersed in PC solution of LiTFSI for storage. The samples were fabricated 3cm x 4cm in size, and cut into 0.5cm x 2.5cm for the bending actuation tests.

2.3 SEM Images of Films

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of CNF/PPy films were taken. For distinguishing, the surface structures of the films were different for electrode and solution sides. The surface contacted to a Ni electrode is called an electrode side and the other surface is called a solution side. Figs. 3(a)-(d) show the electrode sides of different CNF/PPy samples. As seen in the figures, the contribution of CNF is quite different from each other. The sample with higher CNF weight ratio has more CNFs in a certain area, while the sample with lower CNF weight ratio has less. There are so much CNFs can be observed in the image of 10% CNF/PPy sample.

Fig. 3 Figures of samples with different CNF weight ratio, (a)-(d), show the SEM images of electrode sides of 3%, 5%, 7% and 10% CNF/PPy films, (e) shows the solution side of a 5% CNF/PPy film.

SEM images of solution side of the samples look similar to each other. Here take the image of solution side of 5% CNF/PPy for example. Comparing to the electrode side of the samples, the solution side as in Fig. 3(e) is rough and grainy. It consists of lots of PPy balls. It is very different from the electrode side. The different surface situations make the ionic movement different on each side and cause a bending actuation of the samples. It is obvious that, there are much more ions doping into the electrode side than the solution side. The effect of doping of ions on the electrode side is more efficient than the solution side. The deformation happened on the electrode side is larger than that happened on the solution side.

2.4 Control of Polymerization

The polymerization is quite related with the current density and time. In this research, as the other condition is the same (temperature, current density), the situation of polymerization depends on the time only. In order to test the polymerization ratio, several tests were done. Under 0°C, constant dc current was supplied. The current density is 0.2mA/cm². For the pure PPy film, the polymerization speed is about 0.016mm/h (0.12g/h) for the current density 0.2mA/cm², under 0°C. The results are shown in Table 1.

Under this situation, to control the percentage of CNF become possible. The percentage of CNF can be denoted by:

$$P = MC / (MC + MP) \quad (1)$$

where P is the percentage of CNF, MC is the mass

Table 1. Results for test of polymerization ratio

Polymerization conditions	0°C Current density: 0.2mA/cm ²	0°C Current density: 0.2mA/cm ²
Polymerization time	8 hours	20 hours
Thickness	0.13mm	0.32mm
Polymerization speed	0.01625mm/h	0.016mm/h

of CNF, *MP* is mass of polypyrrole. *MC* can be measured it is the weight difference between the electrode with CNF and the neat one. *MP* can be calculated by polymerization ratio and time. So the CNF percentage can be controlled by the polymerization time for the fixed CNF mass.

3 Bending Actuation

Bending actuations were tested for PPy film and CNF/PPy films. A function generator (Agilent 33220a) supplied an $\pm 1.5\text{ V}$ AC driving potential. The PC (200 mL) solution of LiTFSI (2 g) was used as an electrolyte. Bending deformations of single-layer PPy and CNF/PPy films were caused by applying an electric current, while one end of films was fixed to working electrode and the other was free in an electrolyte. A counter electrode (Ni) is needed to form a circuit loop.

Bending actuation can be rarely found in a very thin single-layer film, but usually happens in a bi-layer or tri-layer actuator because of the different strain generate from each layer. Fig. 4 shows the schematic diagram for different structure of bending actuators. A double layer bending actuator works because of the swelling of the polymer layer. A tri-layer bending actuator works under the different movement of the outer two polymer layers. It is a very unique phenomenon that a single-layer thin film can be bent. This phenomenon is due to the different surface situations of solution and electrode sides of the films. The two sides of the single layer

samples are quite different from each other. From Fig. 5 [8], we can see the differences clearly.

The electrode side of the samples is smooth and porous, the solution side of the samples is rough and holes are rarely found on this side. During a redox reaction, much TFSI ions move into the small holes on the electrode side of a film and make holes swell. On the solution side, the amount of TFSI ions which move in to the film is less. In this case, the single layer film can be considered as a bi-layer structure. Therefore, the swelling on the electrode side is more active than the solution side, this cause the bending actuation of the single layer film.

The given AC voltage is 0.5 Hz that means the film can finish 2 bending cycles during 1 second. The bending actuations can decay during the test process. The first bending cycle generate the largest tip deflection. The max tip bending deflection of a 2 cm long PPy film is 1.9 mm, 3% CNF/PPy film showed 1.5 mm max tip bending deflection, 5% CNF/PPy film showed 1.3 mm tip bending deflection and 7% CNF/PPy film showed 1.2 mm tip bending deflection.

The work lifetime of PPy film is 630 cycles, the 3% CNF/PPy can bending for 1020 cycles, the 5% CNF/PPy can bending for 1040 cycles and the 7% CNF/PPy can bending for 1070 cycles. The CNF can increase the working lifetime more than 60%. The bending test is still undergoing. These prove that well-designed CNF/PPy single-layer film possesses a great potential to be used as relatively hard actuators. The working lifetime is the number of cycles counted from the first actuation cycle to the end of the actuation (when the tip deflection decay to 0, no actuation will be operated).

Fig. 4 Schematic diagram for different structures of bending actuators

Fig. 5 SEM photographs of TFSI-doped PPy film prepared on Pt electrode; electrode side (left) and solution side (right). [8]

In order to investigate the electrochemical behavior of conducting polymer, researchers derived equations for the relationship between driven voltage and actuation strain (or tip deflection of bending actuation). It is believed that a typical composite actuator has a cell structure. When a voltage is applied between the reference and the working electrode, ions within the medium are transported by electrophoretic force, with anions and cations traveling parallel to the applied field and in opposite directions. As the ions approach to the interface, the composite surface charges electronically, thereby preventing electric field from penetrating the composite surface.

The ions and charges form what is known in electrochemistry as a double layer capacitor. Following the method that was presented by Madden *et al* [9], to the polypyrrole actuator, the composite actuator admittance transfer function $Y(s)$ can be obtained, which combine the effects of diffusion, capacitance and electrolyte resistance:

$$Y(s) = \frac{\delta + \sqrt{\frac{D_c}{s}} \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{d}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{s}{D_c}}\right)}{\left[\delta + \sqrt{\frac{D_c}{s}} \cdot \tanh\left(\frac{d}{2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{s}{D_c}}\right)\right] \cdot R_e + \frac{\delta}{C_{dl}s}} \quad (2)$$

where, R_e is the resistance of the electrolyte, D_c is the coefficient of ionic diffusion in the composites, C_{dl} is the double layer capacitance, δ is the double

layer separation, d is the thickness of the composite film.

Kim and Liu [10] have developed an equation for the strain of a SWNT/PAni film actuator. The total strain of the composite actuator can be expressed as [10-11]

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_T(s) &= a_1 \cdot \varepsilon_p(s) + a_2 \cdot \varepsilon_C(s) \\ &= \left\{ \left[a_1 \cdot \frac{\alpha}{s \cdot V_f} \cdot s \cdot C_{dl} \cdot \left(\frac{d}{2\delta} + 1 \right) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + a_2 \cdot \frac{0.2 \times (0.1 \times 2\sqrt{3} \mp K) \cdot M_C \cdot C_G \cdot [1 - s \cdot C_{dl} \cdot \left(\frac{d}{2\delta} + 1 \right) \cdot R_e]}{F} \right] \cdot U(s) \right\} \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

where $a_1 = \frac{E_c}{E_T} \cdot V_p$ and $a_2 = \frac{E_p}{E_T} (1 - V_p)$.

In Eq. (3), the electrolyte resistance, R_e , and the thickness of the film, d , can be readily measured; the double layer capacitance, C_{dl} , and the specific capacitance of SWNTs, C_G , also can be measured, fit, or the accepted value can be used; the double layer separation, δ , can be approximately related to $C_{dl} \cdot V_p$ is the polymer volume fraction, E_c and E_p are the Young's modulus of SWNT and conductive polymer, respectively. E_T is the equivalent Young's modulus of composite film. For the given SWNTs that is used to synthesis the composite, K is constant. And we can determine it by identifying this constant to that of pure SWNTs mat actuators. Then the strain of SWNTs well-aligned composite actuator is explicit.

As mentioned in the introduction, conducting polymer actuator works with the motion of ions. There exists a balance between the electric force and a viscous resistance as well as a diffusion force. It can be described by the following equation [7]:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_1 \frac{\partial Q(x,t)}{\partial t} &= kT \frac{\partial^2 Q(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \\ - \frac{\partial Q(x,t)}{\partial x} &\left\{ \frac{e}{\varepsilon_e S_x} \left[\int_0^t i(\tau) d\tau + Q(x,t) - Q(x,0) \right] \right\} \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

The initial and boundary conditions are [12]:

$$\{Q(x,0)\} = N_a e S_x c_0 x \quad (5)$$

$$\{Q(0,t)\} = 0, \{Q(d,t)\} = N_a e S_x c_0 d \quad (6)$$

The electric charge density $c(x,t)$ can be calculated by:

$$Q(x,t) = N_a e S_x \int_0^x c(\xi,t) d\xi \quad (7)$$

The description of the equation in details can be found in references [7] and [12].

Until now, all the equations about the actuation of conducting polymer are based on the movement of ions and charging theory. They considered the equivalent of charging. However, the deformation of polymer is determined by kinds of conditions, such as potential, solution, size of counter ion and so on. In former research, it seems that, the size of ions is not considered. In fact, it is a very important complication should be involved in the equation. It plays a very important role in the electrochemical actuation processing. It should be considered as a key point during the derivation of actuation equations.

There are lots of factors can affect the actuation of conductive polymer. Different ions will cause different actuations when other conditions are the same. For the same ion, higher driven voltage will operate larger actuation strain. Besides, the concentrations of the solution and the solvent type also have different effects on the actuation. In this research, the derivation of actuation equation is based on the size of ions. It is because that, the conducting polymer will give different actuation strain and stress when it working in different solutions. When different ions doped into the polymer, the change of volume is surely different. The reason for this difference is the difference between different ions (size, density, mole mass, charging amount et. al.). It is obvious that the actuation in a big size ion solution is much larger than it operated in small size ion solution. It can be expected that by this property, the conducting polymer is able to be applied in sensors to detect and distinct kinds of ions.

To derive new actuation equations, the first thing to do captures sizes of different ions. Eq. 1 expresses the volume of a single ion:

$$V_i = \frac{M}{N \cdot \rho} \quad (8)$$

where V_i is the volume of a single ion, M is a mole mass of the ion, N is Avogadro constant and ρ is density. In this study, M is 280 g/mol, N is 6.02E23 /mol and ρ is 1.57 g/cm³. Therefore, the volume of a single TFSI- ion is 2.96E-22 cm³.

The maximum volume change in the film can be expressed as:

$$\Delta V = \frac{\int_0^t i(\tau) d\tau}{q} \cdot \frac{M}{N \cdot \rho} \quad (9)$$

where ΔV is volume change, i is electrical current, t is operation time for a half period, q is changing amount of a single electron. Because the operating voltage is expressed as $1.5 \sin(4\pi * t)$, i depends on the resistance which can be calculate from the electrical conductivity measured in this study.

4 Mechanical Properties of CNF/PPy

Because CNF/PPy composite films have been fabricated in our laboratory for the first time by the electrophoretic deposition and polymerization process, the mechanical properties of CNF/PPy are necessary to be obtained by mechanical tests. The universal test machine, Instron UTM 3343, was used for extensional tests. The test specimen films were fabricated and cut into 5 mm x 40 mm. Of 40 mm in length, the gage length is 20 mm and the grip size, 10 mm, was applied on both clips. The blue hill 2 generated test reports including load-extension curves.

Thin CNF/PPy composite single layer films of 0, 3, 5, and 7 CNF wt% were tested. Three same test specimens were fabricated for each CNF wt%. Adding CNF resulted in the increase in Young's modulus of conducting polymer (PPy). Average Young's modulus of pure PPy is 22.523 MPa and that of the 3% CNF/PPy composite film is 30.844 MPa which increases almost 36.9%. Young's modulus of 5% CNF/PPy is 38.369 MPa and that of 7% CNF/PPy film is 40.930 MPa. It is obvious that CNF's can improve Young's modulus of PPy. When the CNF weight ratio increases from 3% to 5%,

Young's modulus increases from 30.844 MPa to 38.369 MPa which increases 24.4%. When CNF weight ratio increase from 5% to 7%, Young's modulus increases from 38.369 MPa to 40.930 MPa. The increase in stiffness is only 6.7%. The enhancement in stiffness is not so efficient after adding 5 wt% of CNF's and the tensile strength increases continuously from 0% to 7%. The tensile test results of pure PPy are summarized in Table 2.

Fig. 6 Picture of Instron UTM 3343

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7 Air pressure clips with and without a specimen

Table 2. Results for tension test of 0% CNF/PPy film (pure PPy film)

	Load at failure (N)	Tensile strain at failure (mm/mm)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Modulus (MPa)	Extension at failure (mm)
1	0.725	0.095	0.967	23.847	1.893
2	0.753	0.102	1.003	22.476	2.035
3	0.731	0.094	0.975	21.246	1.885
mean	0.736	0.097	0.982	22.523	1.938
max	0.753	0.102	1.003	23.847	2.035
min	0.725	0.094	0.967	21.246	1.885

Fig. 8 Load-extension plots from the tensile tests of pure PPy

5. Conclusions

Longitudinal strain and bending behaviors of CNF/PPy films were investigated in order to see the actuating performance of the new material. PPy films showed as high as 12.6% in a longitudinal

strain, while CNF/PPy composite films gave a little lower value (8.6~12.0%). This is because the increased stiffness by adding CNF materials restricts strains of PPy material. However, the strain of CNF/PPy is still large enough to activate a small device with increased actuating forces. It was noticed that bending actuations decayed in the electrical bending test. The largest tip deflections in the first bending cycle were generated for both materials. The max tip bending deflection of a 2cm long PPy film was 1.9 mm, 3% CNF/PPy film showed 1.5 mm max tip bending deflection, 5% CNF/PPy film showed 1.3 mm tip bending deflection and 7% CNF/PPy film showed 1.2 mm tip bending deflection. The working life of pure PPy films was 630 cycles, that of 3% CNF/PPy was 1020 cycles, the 5% CNF/PPy was 1040 cycles and the 7% CNF/PPy was 1070 cycles. Adding CNF increased the life cycle more than 60%. A new bending equation for this material was developed to predict deflections, and the maximum tip deflection of pure PPy film was predicted. The calculated bending result was $y = 2.056\text{mm}$, that is very close to the experimental result of 1.9mm.

A new conducting material, CNF/PPy, for a sensor and an actuator were developed and it showed improved stiffness, longitudinal strains, bending life cycles, electric conductivity than pure PPy material. Larger strain and higher Young's modulus give a high actuation force and improved conductivity means fast responses. Through various tests, this new material was proven to be a good material candidate for smart actuators and sensors.

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